

Working Paper

The new Stability and Growth Pact:
Innovation and Continuity in the Light of
Next Generation EU

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Coming after the breakthrough of NGEU, the proposed reform of the Stability and Growth Pact represents the most radical overhaul of fiscal governance since the launch of EMU. While the original orientations of the Commission, which put national medium-term fiscal structural plans constrained only by debt sustainability standards squarely at the centre of the system, have been traduced in part by the reintroduction of artificial numerical benchmarks, important simplifications remain, largely freeing low-debt Member States from any intrusive surveillance and greatly facilitating the assessment of compliance through a single observable indicator. Both the concept of plans designed by Member States and the trade-off between reforms and investment and more gradual adjustment reflect the influence of the NGEU. The reform does not question, however, the primacy of fiscal sustainability. In spite of the improvements, challenges in implementation and enforcement are bound to persist, essentially reflecting the unresolved tension between the centralisation of monetary policy and national fiscal sovereignty.

Keywords: EMU, economic governance, fiscal rules, Stability and Growth Pact, Next Generation EU

1. Introduction

This chapter discusses the nature and content of European Union (EU) fiscal governance or, to use a shorthand, fiscal rules, that is, supranational rules coordinating and controlling budgetary policies of EU Member States. In particular, the chapter examines the reform of main instrument of coordination and control, the Stability and Growth Pact (SGP,) coming in the wake of breakthrough in economic governance represented by Next Generation EU (NGEU).

The chapter is structured as follows: Section 2 highlights the special nature of coordination and control mechanism of national budgetary policies under EU law and its implications for the EU's ability to interfere with such policies as well undertake a common budgetary policy. Section 3 briefly assesses the SGP experience during the unprecedented emergency represented by the COVID-19 pandemic. Section 4 summarizes the reform process of the SGP while sections 5 and 6 provide a detailed description of and preliminary commentary to both the preventive and corrective arms of the new SGP. Section 7, finally, concludes highlighting the innovations envisaged by the SGP reform, and how they relate to the NGEU 'constitutional' change.

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2. The special nature of the EU fiscal rules

EU fiscal governance rules are originally based in the EU Treaty provisions on economic and monetary policy, namely, Articles 120 TFEU to 126 TFEU.

These provisions on fiscal governance are of special nature owing to two related features:

- There are few substantive rules, with fiscal governance being mainly defined in terms of procedures for EU surveillance of Member States' policies. Beyond the general principle that Member States should "regard their economic policies as a matter of common concern" (Article 121(1) TFEU), ensuring "compliance" with the guiding principles of "stable prices, sound public and monetary conditions and a sustainable balance of payments" (Article 120 and Article 119(3) TFEU), the only provision in the Treaty that comes close to a substantive fiscal rule is that Member States "shall avoid excessive government deficits" (Article 126(1)), itself further defined in terms of a specific surveillance procedure bearing the same name. Outside the excessive deficit procedure, substantive fiscal rules can only be found in secondary legislation, itself based on Treaty provisions allowing for the specification of "rules for the multilateral surveillance" (Article 121(6)) and therefore not capable to generate substantive obligations on Member States.
- The provisions on fiscal governance in the Treaty and in the secondary legislation are not directly applicable, that is, they cannot be enforced by national judicial or administrative authorities overriding any inconsistent national provisions. In other words, the Union has no 'right of veto' on national budgetary policy. The other distinctive cornerstone of EU law, namely, judicial review and enforcement by the Court of Justice, is also signally weaker in the field of fiscal governance than in other areas. The paucity of substantive provisions, coupled with the fact the provisions do not confer justiciable rights on individuals², already limits substantially the scope for judicial review. Moreover, the Treaty, by way of exception (Article 126(10) TFEU), excludes recourse to normal means of enforcement of EU law, namely, the infringement procedure with ultimate recourse to the Court of Justice, for the measures taken in the context of the excessive deficit procedure, envisaging instead an essentially political enforcement process centred on the Commission and the Council.³

The special nature of the fiscal rules is reflected in the wide discretion afforded to the Commission and the Council, according to the usual institutional division of roles, where 'the Commission proposes and the Council decides', at every stage of their implementation.⁴ This is also illustrated by many instances of effective evolution of the rules through concrete decisions of the institutions at unchanged legislation. In turn, this has elicited the need to 'codify' the use of discretion in 'soft law' instruments purporting to provide the common

² In *ADEDI and others v Council of the European Union* T-215/11 the Court dismissed as unreceivable an action for annulment of a decision taken under the EDP, on the grounds that private parties lacked the "direct concern" required by the Treaty for seeking judicial review of a regulatory EU act.

³ For different aspects of the issue of enforcement, see Section 4.3.

⁴ Even the apparently mechanical succession of steps of increasing bindingness in the EDP needs strong qualification in light of the Court ruling that failure by the Council to adopt decisions within the deadlines set in the regulation cannot be regarded as giving rise to an act open to legal challenge for the purpose of annulment (Case C-27/04 *Commission v Council* [2004] paragraph 34).

understanding of the what the rules require, so as to stabilize Member States' expectations about their implementation, in particular, the so-called "Code of Conduct."⁵

Taken together these considerations suggest that fiscal governance is essentially a system of peer pressure among Member States organised in the Council under the impulsion of the Commission. This reflects the fundamental political compromise underlying the creation of Economic and Monetary Union (EMU), whereby the centralisation of monetary policy in the hands of a truly 'federal' institution, the European Central Bank (ECB), was not accompanied by a parallel development in other policy areas.

In particular, regarding fiscal policy, traditionally perceived to lie at the heart of sovereignty, Member States are meant to maintain full control on the size and composition of their budgets and be subject only to coordinating rules excluding direct legal interference with government budgets.

It seems prudent therefore to maintain that the limitations inherent in the special nature of the rules underpinning EU fiscal governance, in turn reflected in the SGP, including the relationship between its two constituent parts, or 'arms', as rooted in the respective Treaty bases⁶, are likely to stay. Without changes to the Treaty bases since the Maastricht Treaty, the control of Member States' budgetary policies would remain essentially 'external', that is, incapable to interfere directly with the conduct of such policies based on the domestic national framework.⁷ In turn, this does not seem consistent with a "federalisation of economic policy at supranational level" taking the NGEU as its point of departure.⁸

3. The Stability and Growth Pact during Covid-19

⁵ Specifications on the implementation of the Stability and Growth Pact and Guidelines on the format and content of Stability and Convergence Programmes (Code of Conduct of the Stability and Growth Pact) < <https://data.consilium.europa.eu/doc/document/ST-9344-2017-INIT/en/pdf> > accessed 21 December 2023. The document, fundamental for the understanding of the working of the surveillance procedures, is adopted in the form of Council conclusions following deliberations in the Economic and Financial Committee (EFC). The current version was adopted in 2017. In addition, the Commission services, which contribute actively to the deliberations of the EFC, have been publishing and updating since 2013 a compilation of all the elements relevant for the understanding of its application of the fiscal rules, the 'Vade Mecum on the Stability and Growth Pact' (*European Economy Institutional Papers* 101, April 2019) < https://economy-finance.ec.europa.eu/system/files/2019-04/ip101_en.pdf > accessed 21 December 2023.

⁶ Council Regulation No 1466/97 on the strengthening of the surveillance of budgetary positions and the surveillance and coordination of economic policies (preventive arm regulation) [1997] L209 and amendments, based on Article 121(6) TFEU; Council Regulation No 1467/97 on speeding up and clarifying the implementation of the excessive deficit procedure (corrective arm or EDP regulation) L209 and amendments., based on Article 126(14) TFEU. For a detailed analysis of the SGP see J P Keppenne, 'Fiscal Rules' in Federico Fabbrini and Marco Venturuzzo (eds), *Research Handbook EU Economic Law* (Edward Elgar 2019)

⁷ For the distinction between 'external' and 'internal' control see J P Keppenne, *op.cit.* 35. Since the Six-pack reform, the two arms of the SGP have been flanked by provisions aiming at harmonizing national budgetary procedures as a complement to the SGP, in particular Council Directive 2011/85 on requirements for budgetary frameworks of the Member State (budgetary framework directive) [2011] OJ L 306/41. According to the same distinction, the provisions of the budgetary framework directive would belong to the 'internal control'. They are not covered in the present chapter.

⁸ For the NGEU as the starting point for a federalisation of economic policies in the EU see Federico Fabbrini, *EU Fiscal Capacity* (Oxford University Press 2022) 66.

In reviewing the experience with the SGP since its Six-Pack reform during the euro-crisis, the Commission 2020 review of economic governance⁹ concluded that the EDP had proved effective in bringing down high government deficits, although largely on the back of a gradually improvement in economic conditions and a mild pro-cyclical relaxation of fiscal policy following the strong pro-cyclical fiscal consolidation in the wake of 2008-2012. Reduction in excessive debt levels however had been largely missing, with debt ratios in fact further diverging across the EU and the Commission refraining from recommending recourse to the recently operationalised EDP for breach of the debt criterion out fear of aggravating widespread deflationary pressures.

Outside the excessive deficit procedure, compliance with the fiscal had continued to be uneven at best, as the Member States with the highest debt levels typically had been the most at fault in reaching the prescribed medium-term objective of close to balance or in surplus of the preventive arm, with the dedicated procedures for its enforcement being rarely activated and showing limited effectiveness.

The fiscal framework had not ensured sufficient differentiation between Member States with markedly different sustainability risks and had grown excessively complex, encompassing a plurality of indicators, partly non-observable, and a variety of escape clauses, in turn reflected in a proliferation of common understandings codified outside the formal legal framework.

Finally, the quality of public finances had been deteriorating, particularly as reflected in stagnating or markedly declining shares of public investment, and progress with structural reform had been stalling.

Against the performance of EU economic and fiscal governance described in the Commission review, the sudden outbreak COVID-19 crisis represented an unprecedented challenge but also an opportunity to show awareness of the lessons learnt from the previous crisis.

The most innovative element of the EU response to the crisis is undoubtedly represented by the NGEU package, in particular the Recovery & Resilience Facility (RRF). The RRF innovates in at least two respects: funding, allowing, for the first time, expenditure for economic, social and territorial cohesion to be financed by borrowing¹⁰; governance, creating a new type of performance-based conditionality tying financial support¹¹ to the implementation of reforms and investments planned by Member States in line with broad policy objectives set at EU level. The extent of the change in the political and institutional balance between the national and EU level, and, within the EU level, between the Council and the Commission, resulting from the new system of economic “governance by funding” is the subject of debate.¹²

Alongside the unprecedented example of vertical fiscal coordination, i.e., between the Member States’ fiscal policies and that of the EU budget, set by the RRF, the COVID-19 crisis has seen also a rare example of horizontal coordination by exception of Member States’ fiscal policies, namely, through an effective suspension of the numerical rules of the SGP allowing Member States to pursue expansionary fiscal policies in tandem with the

⁹ Economic governance review Commission Communication COM/2020/55 final.

¹⁰ See chapter by A Belen Macho in this volume.

¹¹ See chapter by N Moran in this volume.

¹² See chapter by M Partin in this volume.

support to the economy provided by the exceptional deployment of unconventional monetary policies by the ECB.¹³

The modalities of the effective suspension of the fiscal rules of the SGP deserve attention.

Throughout the COVID-19 crisis the Commission issued a series of communications aimed at providing qualitative fiscal policy guidance, followed by annual country-specific recommendations adopted by the Council, in line with the European Semester process of economic policy coordination. At the outbreak of the crisis, the Commission invoked provisions in the preventive and the corrective arm of the SGP, commonly referred to as ‘general escape clause’¹⁴, to avoid constraining Member States’ fiscal policies with quantitative prescriptions, although the ostensible aim of the provisions is to allow departures from the adjustment prescribed under the SGP, in case of “severe economic downturn in the euro area or the union as a

The formulation of the clause for the corrective arm, in particular, would not seem to allow for a suspension of the EDP, since it is simply meant to allow the Commission and the Council to “adopt a revised fiscal trajectory”, without recourse to a stepping up of the procedure, in case the concerned Member State has not delivered the prescribed adjustment against the background of a general economic crisis. Accordingly, to avoid activating the EDP for the evident breaches of the excessive deficit criteria resulting from the crisis, the Commission put forward the argument that the outbreak of the COVID-19 crisis created “a situation of exceptional uncertainty, including for designing a credible path for fiscal policy”, in the light of which “a decision on whether to place Member States in EDP should not be taken.”¹⁵ The argument for not opening EDPs was maintained in subsequent communications¹⁶ including in the fiscal guidance for 2024 issued in early 2023,¹⁷ which announced the resumption of quantitative fiscal guidance, to be specified in the annual country-specific recommendations, thereby acknowledging that the uncertainty of the situation was no longer such as to prevent the design of a credible fiscal path. At the same time, the Commission announced the deactivation of the general escape clause at the end of 2023 and that in the spring of 2024 it would propose the opening of the EDPs based on the breach of the deficit criterion as per the fiscal outturn data of 2023.¹⁸

In the absence of a formal procedure for the activation and the deactivation of the general escape clause, reflecting the narrow scope of the original provisions being meant to work within the normal surveillance procedures and not to suspend them, the orientations put forward by the Commission can be considered as setting a new precedent based on the

¹³ On the distinction between horizontal and vertical economic policy coordination and its operation during the COVID-18 crisis see M Buti and M Messori ‘Euro Area Policy Mix: from Horizontal to Vertical Coordination’ (*CEPR Policy Insight* 113, October 2021) < https://cepr.org/system/files/publication-files/103129-policy_insight_113_euro_area_policy_mix_from_horizontal_to_vertical_coordination.pdf > accessed 13 December 2023.

¹⁴ Commission Communication on the activation of the general escape clause of the Stability and Growth Pact COM/2020/123 final.

¹⁵ 2020 European Semester: country-specific recommendations Commission Communication COM/2020/500 final, p. 4.

¹⁶ One year since the outbreak of COVID-19: fiscal policy response Commission communication COM/2021/105 final; Fiscal policy guidance for 2023 Commission communication COM/2022/85 final;

¹⁷ Fiscal policy guidance for 2024 Commission communication COM/2023/141 final.

¹⁸ *Ibid.*, pp. 6 and 8.

endorsement by the Council in the form of political conclusions and through the its subsequent adoption of country-specific economic policy guidelines.

Although associated with the occurrence of compelling circumstances that could be hardly envisaged by the legislator, the effective suspension of the SGP rules, and especially of the EDP, represents further evidence of the special nature of EU fiscal rules, in particular, the wide discretion afforded to the Commission and the Council, including implementation at variance with the ostensible meaning of the rules.

The COVID-19 experience also illustrates the limits of horizontal economic policy coordination: although interpreted very extensively, the general escape clause works by temporarily removing constraints on Member States' policies from EU fiscal rules. It is essentially for the Member States to decide whether to carry out fiscal policies with the qualitative guidance provided by the Commission. While the extraordinary circumstances of the COVID-19 pandemic rendered the guidance broadly consensual, and the link between access to the RRF funds and compliance with the country-specific guidelines,¹⁹ added a further important incentive for conformity, the same cannot be necessarily expected in other circumstances that may call for positive coordination of fiscal policies.

4. The reform of the EU fiscal governance

As t COVID-19 drew to an end, the Commission followed up on its early review by putting forward orientations for a reform of EU economic governance,²⁰ later followed by detailed legal proposals for a reform of the SGP

While retaining the key features of the system of fiscal rules of the Treaty, and in particular the 3% of GDP deficit threshold as focal point for enforcement, the Commission's orientations represented an important departure from the pre-existing SGP architecture. Two concepts stood out as objectives of the reform:

- National ownership, reflected in national medium-term fiscal structural plans becoming the centrepiece of surveillance. The plans would set out multi-annual fiscal

¹⁹ The RRF regulation stipulates that a Member State's recovery and resilience plan, whose positive assessment by the Commission and subsequent endorsement by the Council is instrumental for the access to the funds (grants and loans) of the facility, should, among other criteria, be assessed based on "whether [it] expected to contribute to effectively addressing all or a significant subset of challenges identified in the relevant country-specific recommendations including fiscal aspects thereof ... or challenges identified in other relevant documents officially adopted by the Commission in the context of the European Semester" (Council Regulation (EU) 2021/241 establishing the Recovery and Resilience Facility [2021] OJ L57/17 Article 19). In practice, however, compliance with the country-specific recommendations was assessed of uniform 'good quality' by the Commission raising questions on the effective value of the broad conditionality embedded in the RRF (see Z. Darvas and L. Welslau 'First Lessons from the Recovery and Resilience Facility for the EU Economic Governance Framework' (Economic Governance Support Unit (EGOV) Study PE 741.478, European Parliament) < [https://www.europarl.europa.eu/RegData/etudes/IDAN/2023/741748/IPOL_IDA\(2023\)741748_EN.pdf](https://www.europarl.europa.eu/RegData/etudes/IDAN/2023/741748/IPOL_IDA(2023)741748_EN.pdf) > accessed 13 December 2023.

²⁰ Communication on orientations for a reform of the EU economic governance framework COM/2022/583 final.

targets meant to put excessively high public debts on a robust downward path and include structural reform and investment commitments. As a counterpart of greater scope for Member States to design their fiscal trajectories, the medium-term dimension of fiscal policy greater stability should be enhanced, through avoidance of frequent revisions of the plans and a more stringent enforcement in case of deviations.

- Fiscal sustainability, reflected in a risk-based approach to surveillance, with ex ante constraints largely applying to high-debt risk situations and ex-post enforcement essentially confined, apart from the case of breach of the 3% of GDP deficit criterion of the EDP, to cases of departure from the fiscal targets by high-risk Member States, through a repurposing of the EDP for breach of the debt criterion. The refocusing of surveillance including the formulation of the target in terms of a single indicator (primary expenditure net of discretionary revenue measure) should result in a substantial simplification of the framework.

The orientations can be seen as an attempt to give a consistent answer to the different shortcomings of the system highlighted by the review of the decade-long experience with the SGP, while maintaining the primacy of fiscal sustainability over other objectives, especially in the phase of enforcement.

The influence of the recent experience with the NGEU can be detected in two aspects of the Commission's orientations: implicitly, by making nationally-decided trajectories, as opposed to trajectories determined by numerical rules, the centre of the new fiscal architecture, thereby significantly increasing the leeway of Member States, especially outside of high-debt risk situations, in addressing their perceived expenditure priorities; explicitly, by making an extension of the adjustment period covered by the plan, a possibility particularly important for high-debt Member States, conditional on time-bound reform and investment commitments addressing common EU priorities, including those already under the NGEU and the related expenditure commitments.

The orientations for the reform of the fiscal framework set out in the Commission communication have been translated into legislative proposals issued by the Commission in April 2023.²¹ The proposed legislation consist of a makeover of the preventive arm of the SGP and an amendment of its corrective arm. The latter essentially concerns the reformulation of the EDP for breach of the debt criterion for the purpose of correcting deviations from the adjustment path in the medium-term fiscal structural plans that are at the centre of the new fiscal architecture outlined in the reform orientations. This is the subject of the revision of the other arm of the SGP, which, from the original purpose of simply preventing breaches of the 3% of GDP deficit criterion, is meant to be, at least from the conceptual point view, the core of the reformed fiscal governance.

The Commission proposal was negotiated by the Member States in the Council which agreed on an amended compromise in December 2023. This will now be subject to negotiations with

²¹ Proposal for a regulation of the European Parliament and the Council on the effective coordination of economic policies and multilateral budgetary surveillance and repealing Council Regulation (EC) No 1466/97 COM/2023/240 final; Proposal for a Council regulation amending Regulation (EC) No 1467/97 on speeding up and clarifying the implementation of the excessive deficit procedure COM/2023/241 final. Together with these two proposals, corresponding to the preventive and corrective arm, respectively, the Commission also presented a proposal for a Council directive amending Directive 2011/85/EU on requirements for budgetary frameworks of the Member States.

the European Parliament, which is a co-legislature in the preventive arm, and must be consulted for the legislation on the corrective arm of the SGP.²² The analysis that follows is mainly concerned with the new preventive arm of the SGP, which provides also the key for analysing the much less substantial changes in the corrective arm.

5. The new preventive arm of the Stability and Growth Pact

5.1. *The medium-term fiscal structural plans: early guidance from the Commission to Member States*

The key provisions of the new preventive arm of the SGP can be grouped under three headings corresponding to the main stages of the new surveillance process.

The first group of provisions concerns the early guidance that the Commission is expected to provide Member States to inform the preparation of medium-term fiscal structural plans. The guidance takes the form of “technical trajectories” for “net expenditure,”²³ covering “a period of 4 years and its possible extension by a maximum of 3 years,”²⁴ which the Commission should transmit to concerned Member States and the Economic and Financial Committee (EFC).²⁵

The technical trajectories should be “risk-based and differentiated for each Member State”²⁶ ensuring that by the end of the adjustment period at the latest, assuming a linear adjustment effort “as a rule” and no further budgetary policy measures thereafter, “the projected government debt ratio is put or remains on a plausibly downward path, or stays at prudent levels below 60%” and the “projected general government deficit is maintained below [the 3% of GDP] reference value” over the medium term.²⁷ The Member States concerned are those, whose debt exceeds 60% of GDP or deficit exceeds 3% of GDP.²⁸ For the other

²² Proposal for a Regulation of the European Parliament and of the Council on the effective coordination of economic policies and multilateral budgetary surveillance and repealing Council Regulation (EC) No 1466/97 - Mandate for negotiations with the European Parliament < <https://data.consilium.europa.eu/doc/document/ST-15874-2023-REV-4/en/pdf> > accessed 22 December 2023; Proposal for a Council Regulation amending Regulation (EC) No 1467/97 on speeding up and clarifying the implementation of the excessive deficit procedure - Agreement in principle with a view to consulting the European Parliament < <https://data.consilium.europa.eu/doc/document/ST-15876-2023-REV-4/en/pdf> > accessed 22 December 2023. They are henceforth denoted as Proposal repealing Regulation 1466/97 and Proposal amending Regulation 1467/97. Together with these two proposals, the Council also adopted an agreement in principle on a Proposal for a Council directive amending directive 2011/85/EU on requirements for budgetary frameworks of the Member States.

²³ ‘Net expenditure’ is defined as “government expenditure net of interest expenditure, discretionary revenue measures, expenditure on programmes of the Union fully matched by revenue from Union funds, cyclical elements of unemployment benefit expenditure, and one-offs and other temporary measures” (Article 2 of Proposal for repealing Regulation 1466/97. It closely resembles the aggregate used to assess compliance with the “expenditure benchmark” in the current preventive arm.

²⁴ Article 5 of Proposal for repealing Regulation 1466/97.

²⁵ The Commission should transmit the technical trajectory “at the latest by 15 January of the year in which the Member States have to submit their medium term fiscal-structural plans ... or, within 3 weeks from the request of the Member State to submit a revised plan” (Article 7(1) of Proposal for repealing Regulation 1466/97). The transitory provisions concerning “the first cohort of medium-term fiscal-structural plans” postpone the deadline for transmitting the technical trajectories to 15 February 2024 (Article 38bis(a)).

²⁶ Article 6 of Proposal for repealing Regulation 1466/97.

²⁷ Article 6 of Proposal for repealing Regulation 1466/97. From the Commission Debt Sustainability Monitor (see note 26 below) one can infer a 10-year length for the medium term.

²⁸ Article 5 of Proposal for repealing Regulation 1466/97.

Member States the Commission should provide on request “technical information” on the fiscal position sufficient to ensure respect of the deficit of the risk-based requirements, “indicating whether this implies adjustment needs.”²⁹

In providing the “technical trajectories” and the “technical information” the Commission should include “the underlying debt projections and results” and “the macroeconomic and fiscal assumptions.”³⁰ The methodology for the projections, including for assessing the “plausibility” of the fiscal adjustment path ensuring respect of the of the risk-based requirements, should be adopted by the Council by implementing decision on proposal by the Commission following an opinion by the EFC.³¹ In applying the methodology for the purposes of providing early guidance, the Commission should provide, when transmitting the technical trajectories to the Member States and the EFC, all the relevant information to ensure replicability of results³² and made it public at the time of the submission by the Member States of the fiscal-structural plans.³³

In addition to the above-described risk-based requirements related to the projected trajectories for debt and deficit, the technical trajectories should ensure respect of two other requirements:

- Debt sustainability safeguard:³⁴ the debt-to-GDP ratio should decrease by at a minimum annual average amount of 1% of GDP or 0.5% of GDP, as long it exceeds 90 and 60, respectively. Respect of the requirement should be ensured over the adjustment period (as opposed to the subsequent medium-term projection period relevant for the respect of the risk-based requirements), taking as a base year “the year before the start of the technical trajectory” or, for Member States subject to the EDP, “the year in which the ... procedure is projected to be abrogated.”³⁵
- Deficit resilience safeguard:³⁶ the deficit should (eventually) reach a level of 1.5% of GDP (in structural terms). Respect of the requirement should “ensure that fiscal adjustment continue, where needed, until the Member State reaches [the 1.5% of GDP] deficit level” through “an annual improvement in the primary structural of [at least] 0.4% of GDP, ...reduced to 0.25% of GDP in case of an extension of the adjustment period”. The requirement to reach a structural deficit of 1.5% of GDP is explicitly motivated on grounds of providing a “common resilience margin ... relative to 3% of GDP Treaty reference value”.

²⁹ Article 7(2) of Proposal for repealing Regulation 1466/97.

³⁰ Article 8(1) of Proposal for repealing Regulation 1466/97.

³¹ Article 8 of Proposal for repealing Regulation 1466/97. Recital 14quater envisages that “for the first round of plans, the plausibility of public debt declining in the medium term should be based on the methodology described in the [Commission] Debt Sustainability Monitor 2022” and that the Commission should subsequently propose changes to the methodology for adoption by the Council, following the findings of a working group on debt sustainability (composed by national experts, the Commission and the ECB).

³² Article 7 (1) of Proposal for repealing Regulation 1466/97.

³³ Article 8 of Proposal for repealing Regulation 1466/97.

³⁴ Article 6bis of Proposal for repealing Regulation 1466/97.

³⁵ The provision is silent on the possibility that a Member State might be projected to exit the EDP after the end of the adjustment period, in which case presumably the debt sustainability safeguard would simply not apply.

³⁶ Article 6ter of Proposal for repealing Regulation 1466/97. The margin is defined as “1.5% of GDP in structural terms relative to the 3% of GDP deficit”. This is interpreted here as equivalent to a 1.5% deficit target in structural terms.

The interaction between the primary risk-based requirements and the additional safeguards bears careful consideration. In particular, the deficit resilience safeguard appears to imply that the technical trajectory should be such that the adjustment not only ensures that:

- i) by the end of the adjustment period, debt (if exceeding 60% of GDP) is put on a plausibly downward path and deficit remains below 3% of GDP in the medium term; and
- ii) within the adjustment period (except for a (sub-)period covered by EDP), debt, if above 60% or 90% of GDP, decreases on average by 1% of GDP or 0.5% per year;

but also that:

- iii) the deficit reaches 1.5% of GDP in structural terms. In particular, to the extent that the adjustment required under i) and ii) is not sufficient to reach the additional 1.5% of GDP target, it should be supplemented by further adjustment, up to a total of: 0.4% of GDP per year, if the target is within reach by the end of the ‘default’ 4-year adjustment period; if not, up to a total of 0.25% of GDP per year, until the target is reached. Note that, conceivably, the adjustment may have to continue beyond the maximum 7-year adjustment period covered by the technical trajectory, which would seem a self-contradictory requirement. A possible interpretation would be that any residual adjustment needed for the deficit to reach the 1.5% target beyond the 7-year period would be ensured by the new technical trajectory that the Member State would receive ahead of the submission of a new fiscal structural plan (see below for the process of submission or revision of fiscal structural plans).

It should be stressed that the requirements implied by the additional safeguards apply only to Member States that are recipient of technical trajectories, that is, Member States,³⁷ whose debt exceeds 60% of GDP or deficit exceeds 3% of GDP.

5.2. Preparation and submission of the plans

The second group of provisions concern the preparation and submission of the national medium-term fiscal structural plans by Member States and their assessment by the Commission and subsequent endorsement by the Council.

Following the provision of the early guidance by the Commission, each Member State is to publicly submit to the Commission and the Council a national medium-term fiscal structural plan “containing the fiscal, reform and investment commitments of a Member State, covering

³⁷ While the debt sustainability safeguard applies by definition only to Member States with a debt ratio in excess of 60, the deficit resilience safeguard is apparently formulated to apply to all Member States, and its application to a restricted set of Member States (i.e., with debt ratio in excess of 60 or deficit in excess of 3% of GDP) is inferred only from the definition of technical trajectories. This implies that, once a Member State brings its debt ratio below 60 or the deficit below 3% of GDP, the 1.5% of GDP structural balance target should no longer be relevant. The rationale for imposing a 1.5% target for Member States with low debt, whose deficit may occasionally exceed 3% of GDP, appears questionable, not least because for such Member States the SGP allows dispensing with the opening of the EDP in case of breach of the 3% of GDP deficit threshold.

a planning horizon of 4 years or 5 years depending on the regular length of the national legislature.”³⁸

The fiscal commitments take the form of a “multiannual net expenditure path as well as the underlying macroeconomic assumptions and the planned fiscal-structural measures” showing “compliance with ... fiscal requirements” corresponding to the risk-based requirements and the additional safeguards as defined for the technical trajectories.³⁹ The net expenditure path in the plan need not coincide with that in the technical trajectory, but, if path is “higher” in the plan than in the trajectory, the Member State should provide “sound and data-driven economic arguments explaining the difference.”⁴⁰

The reform and investment commitments are expected to correspond to “the main challenges identified in the European Semester, and in particular, the country-specific recommendations and the common priorities of the Union including achieving a fair green and energy transition, strengthening social and economic resilience and where necessary, the build-up of defence capabilities.”⁴¹ With the exception of the build-up of defence capabilities, the objectives of the reforms and investments in the plan closely mirror the general objectives the eligibility conditions of recovery and resilience plans (RRPs) that Member States had to submit to access the RRF funds.⁴² Unlike those in the RRF, however, the reform and investment commitments in fiscal-structural plans do not require translation into detailed measures including timelines for implementation and progress indicators.

Requirements that are ostensibly closer to those for the RRFs apply to the reform and investment commitments that a Member State should undertake in order to obtain an extension of “the adjustment period [covered by the plan] by 3 years at most.”⁴³ In this case each of the reform and investment commitments should be “sufficiently detailed, front-loaded, time-bound and verifiable” and include “indicators, where relevant, to allow the assessment of their implementation and monitoring,” with implementation (for reforms) or “significant progress” towards it (for investments) within the plan’s horizon. While the reform and investment commitments underpinning the extension of the adjustment period share the general objectives related to challenges identified at EU level, they are especially focused on an improvement of “growth potential” and “support of fiscal sustainability”⁴⁴. The latter, in particular, is absent, at least as an explicit objective, from the objectives of the RRF, while it naturally follows from the overall objective of “sound and sustainable finances” of the SGP. The extension of the adjustment period is also subject to an additionality condition

³⁸ Article 9 and 2(5) of Proposal for repealing Regulation 1466/97. The plan is to be submitted “by 30 April of the last year of the plan in force”. The 30 April deadline for submitting the plan is confirmed in the transitory provisions concerning “the first cohort of medium-term fiscal-structural plans” together with the possibility for “the Member State and the Commission to agree to extend the deadline by a reasonable period of time” (Article 38bis(a)).

³⁹ Article 11(a) of Proposal for repealing Regulation 1466/97. The requirements are defined by reference to the provision for the assessment of the plans by the Commission (Article 15), which in turn refers to the requirements for the technical trajectories. Member States that are not recipient of technical trajectories should therefore be considered subject only to the risk-based requirements.

⁴⁰ Article 11(b) of Proposal for repealing Regulation 1466/97.

⁴¹ Article 11(c) of Proposal for repealing Regulation 1466/97.

⁴² Regulation (EU) 2021/241 of the European Parliament and of the Council of 12 February 2021 establishing the Recovery and Resilience Facility (RRF regulation) [2021] OJ L57 and amendments, Articles 4 and 17.

⁴³ Article 13(1) of Proposal for repealing Regulation 1466/97.

⁴⁴ Article 13(2)(i) and 13(2)(ii) of Proposal for repealing Regulation 1466/97.

missing, at least, explicitly from the RRF,⁴⁵ namely, that “nationally financed public investment over the lifetime of the national medium-term fiscal-structural plan is higher than the medium-term level before the period of that plan.”⁴⁶ Two transitory provisions related to the RRF apply to the extension of the adjustment period⁴⁷ and the assumption of a linear adjustment effort “as a rule” (no-backloading condition)⁴⁸, respectively. The provisions on the duration of the fiscal-structural plans bear scrutiny, in light of the original goal of enhancing the medium-term dimension of fiscal policy.

The definition of the fiscal structural plan takes the length of the national legislature (4 or 5 years) as the reference for the duration of the plan.⁴⁹ This is the same period over which a “newly appointed government may submit a revised medium-term fiscal structural plan.”⁵⁰ While this provision appears to address the case of a new government coming to power following the renewal of the legislature, a more general possibility of a revision covering “the period running until the end of the initial term of the plan” is envisaged “if there are objective circumstances preventing [the plan’s] implementation.”⁵¹ Such circumstances may refer to the case of a change in government occurring at unchanged legislature. This would seem confirmed by the provision according to which the “new technical trajectory”, which the Commission should issue following a Member State’s request to submit a revised plan, should “not allow backloading of the fiscal adjustment effort and [should] not lead as a rule to a lower fiscal adjustment effort.”⁵² This provision seems meant to avoid that the simple appointment of a new government may serve to renege upon the fiscal adjustment commitments taken by its predecessor. The intent of avoiding frequent revisions of the plans is also apparent from the stipulation that revised plans are subject to the same specifications

⁴⁵ Article 5(1) and Article 9 of the RRF regulation stipulate, respectively, that “financial support from the Facility shall not, unless for duly justified cases, substitute recurring national budgetary expenditure and shall respect the principle of additionality of the Union funding” and that “financial support under the Facility should be additional to the support provided under other Union programmes and instruments”.

⁴⁶ Article 13(2)(v) of Proposal for repealing Regulation 1466/97.

⁴⁷ Article 38bis(b) clarifies that the reform and investment commitments contained in the RRFs should be taken into account, provided they “include significant reforms and investments aimed at improving fiscal sustainability and enhancing the growth potential of the economy” and “the Member State concerned commits to continue the reform effort over the remainder of the national medium-term fiscal structural plan, as well as to maintain the nationally financed investment levels realised on average over the period covered by the Recovery and Resilience Plan.” The first condition reflects the focus of the reform on growth potential and fiscal sustainability. The second condition presumably reflects the intention to avoid a slackening of the reform and investment commitments after the lifetime of the RRF (2020-2026).

⁴⁸ Article 38bis(c) stipulates “projects related to the RRF loans and national co-financing of EU funds in 2025 and 2026 shall be taken into account whenever a Member State requests an exception to the no-backloading safeguard.” It should be noted that the condition is qualified “as a rule”, according to established practice, an exception would require a satisfactory justification, but should not be considered as ruled out outside the specific case described in the transitory provision.

⁴⁹ A question arises on whether the maximum duration of the adjustment period including its possible extension should be considered to be 7 or 8 years, depending on the length of the national legislature (4 or 5 years): the former would be consistent with the provisions on the technical trajectories (Article 6), the latter would follow from the ostensible reading of the provisions on the extension of the adjustment period (Article 13) but would introduce an inequality of treatment across Member States. Article 2(7) clarifies that the adjustment period covers “a period of 4 years or, in the case of an extension, a period of 4 years plus an additional extended period of 3 years at the most.”

⁵⁰ Article 14(1)(a) of Proposal for repealing Regulation 1466/97.

⁵¹ Article 14(1) of Proposal for repealing Regulation 1466/97.

⁵² Article 14(3) of Proposal for repealing Regulation 1466/97.

on format and content, including the possibility of an extension of the adjustment period, and the same procedure for assessment and endorsement, as the original plans.⁵³

Excluding a lowering of the fiscal adjustment effort is likely to reduce the incentives for a Member State's in requesting a revision of the plan.⁵⁴ There may be cases, however, where the pursuit of the planned fiscal adjustment can be considered if not unfeasible, at least problematic.

In particular, a revision including the planned fiscal adjustment may be considered necessary to regulate the aftermath of the application of the "escape clauses" of the SGP and the abrogation of an EDP, respectively. Although being subject to EDP does not exclude the application of the procedural and substantial requirements associated with fiscal-structural plans, considerations of legal basis and settled practice strongly suggest that, in case of inconsistency, the prescriptions related to the EDP, and, more specifically, the prescriptions in the EDP decisions addressed to the concerned Member State, should prevail.⁵⁵ This includes the prescriptions on abrogation, which, at least for deficit-based EDPs, revolve around meeting the 3% of GDP threshold. In turn, this may imply that a Member State exiting the EDP may find itself in situation of non-compliance with the requirements of its fiscal-structural plan. A revision of the plan, including the adjustment effort, would seem the rational solution to such inconsistency.

Other cases for a revision of the plan including the adjustment effort cannot be excluded, particularly in the light of the "as a rule" qualification of the provision against a lowering of the effort. An extensive recourse to such possibility would however effectively undermine the goal of enhancing the medium-term dimension of fiscal policy and reproduce the pattern of repeated postponement of the achievement of the fiscal objectives typical of the preventive arm.

A question related to, but distinct from, that of the revision of the fiscal-structural plans is how to reconcile the provision that the duration of the plans should coincide with the regular length of the national legislature with the possibility of an extension of the adjustment period, by a maximum of 3 years.

⁵³ Article 14(4) of Proposal for repealing Regulation 1466/97.

⁵⁴ Although the underlying macro-fiscal scenario is likely to have changed from the time of the submission of the original plan, compliance with the rules is to be assessed exclusively against delivery of the "fiscal adjustment effort" in the original plan. Being formulated in terms of "net primary expenditure", the adjustment effort is supposed to be "not affected by ... expenditure [and revenue] fluctuations outside the direct control of the government" (Recital 12). This is presumably the reason for the presumption that the adjustment effort should not be altered (lowered) in the revised plan. Although not corresponding to a literal reading of relevant provisions, a possible question is whether the submission of a revised plan would have the effect of setting to zero the cumulated deviations against the net expenditure path in the original plan recorded in the control account (see below Section 4.2.4).

⁵⁵ The primacy of the specific prescriptions of the EDP over the general provisions of the preventive arm is confirmed by the current practice whereby, for Member States subject to EDP, the 'annual fiscal recommendation', part of the annual country-specific recommendations in the context of the European Semester (based on Article 121(3) TFEU), is limited to a confirmation that they should abide by EDP recommendation that they have received. The Proposal for repealing Regulation 1466/97 confirms the primacy of the EDP by stipulating, under the risk-based requirements for the technical trajectories, that they should ensure "consistency with the corrective path ... in Regulation (EC) No 1467/97" (Article 6).

Assuming that, in case of extension, the same plan should apply beyond the length of the national legislature would appear to contradict the explicit provisions defining the plans and allowing for their revision as well as the underlying considerations of political legitimacy.

The alternative, more plausible, assumption is therefore that, in case of the extension, while the “planning horizon” of plan is meant to extend beyond the 4 or 5-year length of the national legislature, by the end of the legislature the concerned Member State should submit a new plan, the starting point of which should presumably be the extension of the adjustment path in the previous plan and the corresponding reforms and investments, with the adaptations made necessary by the changes in the underlying macro-fiscal scenario.⁵⁶ In this connection it appears also relevant the provision applying in case of revision of the plan, whereby “the Commission should in particular assess, if applicable, whether any extension of the adjustment period is to apply or continue to apply under the revised national medium-term fiscal structural plan.”⁵⁷

While the requirements that the fiscal-structural plans should satisfy, including the conditions for an extension of the adjustment period, are sufficiently detailed in the legislation, their application to concrete situations may be challenging.

The legislation already explicitly envisages that the adjustment path in the plan submitted by a Member State may not coincide with the technical trajectory issued by the Commission. Such differences can be expected to arise as the standard technical assumptions used by the Commission services to produce the technical trajectories, e.g., about the cyclical position of the economy and the response of revenues to its evolution, are replaced by assumptions better reflecting country-specific situations.

Differences of views may arise concerning the interpretation of the requirements, for example the conditions for an extension of the adjustment period, or the revision of a plan. To allow for the resolution of such differences before the official submission of the plan, in particular, concerning the requirements that plans and their revisions should respect, Member States are expected “to hold with the Commission a technical dialogue.”⁵⁸

The provision on technical dialogue can be seen as reflecting and formalizing the experience of the intense contacts between Member States and the Commission during the preparations of the RRFs, with a view to avoiding in advance that the plans be found not satisfying the criteria in the legislation for their eventual assessment.⁵⁹

5.3. Assessment and endorsement of the plans

⁵⁶ Recital 24bis makes an explicit reference to reforms and investments carrying through successive plans by stipulating that “the impact of investment and reform commitments, once implemented within the medium-term fiscal structural plans will be duly taken into account in the design of subsequent plans.”

⁵⁷ Article 14(5) of Proposal for repealing and replacing Regulation 1466/97.

⁵⁸ Article of Proposal for repealing and replacing Regulation 1466/97.

⁵⁹ The RRF regulation only implicitly refers to a technical dialogue between the Commission and the Member States before the official submission of the RRFs, specifically, in stipulating that “When carrying out that assessment, the Commission shall act in close cooperation with the Member State concerned. The Commission may make observations or seek additional information. The Member State concerned shall provide the requested additional information and may revise the recovery and resilience plan if needed, *including after* the official submission of the recovery and resilience plan” (Article 19 italics added).

Following the official submission of a plan by a Member State, the Commission should assess it,⁶⁰ specifically, by examining:

- For all Member States, that the net expenditure path in the plan complies with the common risk-based requirements related to the projected trajectories for debt and deficit (i.e., that debt be put on a plausibly downward path toward, or stay at prudent levels below, 60% of GDP and the deficit be maintained below 3% of GDP, in the medium term).⁶¹
- For Member States recipient technical trajectory, that, in addition to the above risk-based requirements, the net expenditure path complies with the debt sustainability safeguard and the deficit resilience safeguard.⁶²
- For the Member States requesting an extension of the adjustment period, whether the reforms and investment commitments underpinning the request comply with the required conditions.⁶³

Following the assessment by the Commission, the fiscal-structural plan is the subject of a decision by the Council (technically, a recommendation⁶⁴), on recommendation by the Commission, where three possible outcomes are envisaged:

- Endorsement of the plan submitted by the Member State, specifically, “setting the net expenditure path ... and, if applicable, endorsing the set of reform and investment commitments underpinning an extension of the adjustment period.”⁶⁵
- Request that the Member State “submits a revised national medium-term fiscal-structural plan”, specifically, in case the Council “considers that the plan does not comply with the requirements [that apply to Member States recipient of a technical trajectory] and [that apply to the Member States requesting an extension of the adjustment period].”⁶⁶

⁶⁰ The Commission is expected to assess each plan “within six weeks of its submission”, a deadline extendable by “up to two weeks as rule if necessary” by common agreement between the Commission and the concerned Member State” (Article 15(1) of Proposal for repealing Regulation 1466/97)

⁶¹ Article 15(1a) of Proposal for repealing and replacing Regulation 1466/97. Note that the assumption of a linear adjustment effort “as a rule” (no backloading condition) strictly does not apply to the endorsement of all Member States’s plans, because it is enunciated in connection with requirements for the technical trajectories.

⁶² Article 15(2) of Proposal for repealing and replacing Regulation 1466/97. A question might arise, should the net expenditure path in the plan not satisfy the debt sustainability safeguard owing to ‘below the line’ operational, are typically not included in the technical trajectories that are produced according to standard assumptions.

⁶³ Article 15(3) of Proposal for repealing and replacing Regulation 1466/97. The same provision refers also to compliance with the requirements for “other reforms and investment”, i.e. those in the context of the European Semester and those addressing country-specific recommendations, as if such requirements applied only to a subset of Member States.

⁶⁴ As the submission, assessment and endorsement of fiscal-structural plans are to be included in the European Semester (Article 3 of Proposal for repealing and replacing Regulation 1466/97), the recommendation should be based on Article 121(2) TFEU.

⁶⁵ Article 16 of Proposal for repealing and replacing Regulation 1466/97.

⁶⁶ Article 17 of Proposal for repealing and replacing Regulation 1466/97. The use of the “and” condition would literally imply that the revision of the plan should be requested only if both the fiscal requirements (for Member States recipient of a technical trajectory) and the reform and investment requirements (for Member States requesting an extension of the adjustment period) are not complied with. This does not seem logical and therefore the “and” should presumably be replaced by “or”.

- Determination that “the technical trajectory issued by the Commission be as a rule the net expenditure path of the Member State”⁶⁷ in one of the following cases: i) the Member State concerns fails to submit a revised national medium-term fiscal structural plan within one month of the [Council’s request to do so]”; ii) “the revised national medium-term fiscal-structural plan [continues] not [to] comply with the requirements [that apply to Member States recipient of a technical trajectory] and [that apply to the Member States requesting an extension of the adjustment period]”; iii) “the Member State fails to submit an initial national medium-term fiscal-structural plan or a new national medium-term fiscal-structural plan in the last year covered by the ongoing national medium-term fiscal-structural plan.”

The provisions on the endorsement of the fiscal-structural plans, or the lack thereof, appear to concern Member States with a debt ratio in excess of 60 or a deficit ratio in excess of 3 (as they are the only recipients of technical trajectories).

The Member States not recipient of a technical trajectory do not appear to face a possible request to submit a revised plan nor (by definition) are subject to the possibility that the technical trajectory be imposed on them.⁶⁸ For these Member States therefore endorsement of the plan appears the only possibility. This raises the question of the extent of possible modifications that the Council might introduce in the net expenditure path, if it considers that it does not comply with the risk-based requirements, which, unlike the safeguards, apply to all Member States.⁶⁹ A case for modification of the net expenditure path might also arise if the plan departed from the technical trajectory without providing adequate justification, for example by relying on unduly favourable macro-fiscal assumptions.⁷⁰

Finally, the provisions on the assessment and endorsement of the plans contemplate the possibility that a Member State, which has been granted an extension of the adjustment period, fails to deliver on the reforms and investment commitments underpinning the extension. In this case it is envisaged that “the Council may on recommendation by the Commission recommend “revised net expenditure path with a shorter adjustment period, unless there are objective circumstances preventing implementation by the initially foreseen deadline.”⁷¹

⁶⁷ Article 18 of Proposal for repealing and replacing Regulation 1466/97.

⁶⁸ Strictly speaking, a revision of the plan may be asked in case of non-compliance with the investment and reform commitments underpinning an extension of the adjustment period. However, Member States with a debt ratio below 60 and a deficit ratio below 3 are however unlikely to be interested in an extension.

⁶⁹ The formulation of Article 16 seems to leave open the possibility that, in endorsing the plan, the Council sets out a net expenditure path the does not coincide with that in the plan submitted by the Member State. This possibility should be distinguished from the simple imposition of the net expenditure path of the technical trajectory, which is reserved to cases of non-submission or repeated non-compliance with the fiscal requirements or the reform and investment requirements.

⁷⁰ Recital 20 states that “The Commission’s assessment of the national medium-term fiscal-structural plans should examine in particular the plausibility of the macroeconomic and fiscal assumptions, to the extent that they differ from those underlying the technical trajectory. In particular, the debt projections at unchanged policy to be included in the plan should be comparable with the Commission projections.” These provisions are not to be found in any of the articles of the Proposal for repealing Regulation 1466/97, however. The reference to the debt trajectory, in particular, raises the question of differences due to ‘below-the-line’ operations not included in the debt trajectory.

⁷¹ Article 19 of Proposal for repealing and replacing Regulation 1466/97.

It may seem natural to compare this provision with those in the RRF regulation concerning the case of a Member State not delivering on the milestones and targets after the adoption of its RRP by the Council.

In terms of procedure, the RRF demands to the Commission the decision to authorize or not the disbursement of funds upon fulfilment of the relevant milestones and targets, with the Council exercising an indirect power on the decision.⁷² On substance, the decision not to disburse funds or, rather, to only partially disburse funds under the RRF, does not have the irreversible character of the Council decision to shorten the adjustment period, with likely consequences on the ability of the concerned Member State to comply with new more demanding expenditure path.

This suggests that the recourse by the Council to the possibility of shortening the adjustment period in case of a Member State's failure to deliver on the investment and reform commitments may suffer from a problem of time consistency and therefore be unlikely to be put in practice.

5.4. Implementation of the plans and surveillance

The third and final group of provisions replacing the preventive arm of the SGP concerns the implementation of the national medium-term fiscal-structural plans.

Member States are to publicly submit to the Commission “an annual progress report on the implementation of its national medium-term fiscal plan.”⁷³ The report should “contain in particular information about the progress in the implementation of the net expenditure path, the implementation of broader reforms and investments in the European Semester context and, if applicable, in the implementation of the set of reforms and investments underpinning an extension of the adjustment period.”⁷⁴ The information in the report should be used by the Commission, together with other relevant information, to carry out surveillance of the implementation of the plan in the context of the European Semester⁷⁵.

The surveillance is expected to take the usual form of annual country-specific recommendations and employment guidelines as envisaged by Article 121(2) and Article 148(2) TFEU, respectively.⁷⁶

Failure to act by a Member State upon the guidance received may result in: i) a further [country-specific] recommendation [in accordance to Article 121(2)]; ii) a warning by the Commission or a recommendation by the Council by the Council in accordance with Article 121(4); iii) measures under the EDP regulation⁷⁷. The consequences of failure to act are enumerated in an ascending order of gravity. It should be stressed that the measure under i)

⁷² The disbursement of funds is authorized by an implementing act subject to the qualified majority opinion of the Member States according to the examination procedure for the control of the Commission's exercise of implementing powers (RRF regulation, Recital 69).

⁷³ Article 20(1) of Proposal for repealing Regulation 1466/97. The deadline for the submission of the report is 30 April, that is, the same for the submission of the original plan.

⁷⁴ Article 21(3) of Proposal for repealing Regulation 1466/97.

⁷⁵ Article 21(4a) of Proposal for repealing Regulation 1466/97.

⁷⁶ Article 4(2) of Proposal for repealing Regulation 1466/97.

⁷⁷ Article 4(3) of Proposal for repealing Regulation 1466/97.

and ii) are not backed by effective enforcement provisions, owing to the already noted weak legal basis represented by Article 121 TFEU⁷⁸.

The EDP, by contrast, is potentially backed by significant sanctions, at least for euro-area Member States, but its use for enforcing the implementation of the fiscal-structural plan, concerns only Member State with debt in excess of 60% of GDP, as it will be shown. The main instrument for the Commission to monitor the implementation of the net expenditure path in the plan is a “control account to keep track of cumulative upward and downward deviations of actual net expenditure from the net expenditure path”, with a debit being recorded when “the actual net expenditure [recorded on the basis of outturn data] in the concerned Member State in a given year is above the net expenditure path set by the Council” and a credit in the opposite case. The “cumulated balance” of the account is defined as “the sum of the yearly debits and credits ... expressed in percentage of GDP and the account should be “reset after the endorsement by the Council of a new medium-term fiscal-structural plan.”⁷⁹

The provision on the control account confirms that, once the net expenditure path in the fiscal structural plan has been endorsed, indicators others than the net expenditure path (e.g., the trajectory of debt, the change and the level of the structural balance) become irrelevant, at least until the submission of a new plan or its revision. In this sense, therefore, the proposal, remains faithful to the principle of the single operational indicator of the original Commission orientations for reform, in spite of the addition of several new elements making it more difficult to read.

This represents an important change with respect to the current set-up of fiscal rules, where surveillance relies on several indicators in both assessing fiscal plans and outcomes (e.g., change in the structural balance and expenditure benchmark). Moreover, the construction of the new single indicator, which excludes revisions in the underlying measure of economic growth and over- and underperformances of revenue unrelated to government policies, has superior properties of predictability and countercyclicality. Important specifications are missing, however, on how deviations will be measured, other than they will be expressed as percentage of GDP. In particular, it is not specified whether deviations will be measured relative to planned levels or planned changes in net expenditure, and whether GDP and inflation will be measured in actual or planned terms⁸⁰.

The provisions on implementation of the plans are completed by two escape clauses, one of general, the other of country-specific application.

⁷⁸ The current preventive arm regulation includes an elaborate procedure, the significant deviation procedure, to escalate pressure on Member State deviating from the prescribed adjustment path the MTO, including strict deadlines for adopting warning and recommendations as well as recourse to reverse simple majority voting for the final determination of no effective action. For euro area Member States, no effective action should be followed by the imposition of an “interest-bearing deposit” in accordance to the same effective enforcement of budgetary surveillance regulation used to introduce early sanctions under the EDP (see note 12 above). The significant deviation procedure remains affected by the fundamental weakness of its legal basis in the Treaty (Article (121(4)) TFEU). The procedure is not mentioned in the Proposal for repealing Regulation 1466/97 and should therefore be considered as repealed by the proposed reform.

⁷⁹ Article 21 of Proposal for repealing Regulation 1466/97.

⁸⁰ Recital 33 of Proposal for repealing Regulation 1466/97 mentions (an update of) the Code of Conduct “to ensure effective implementation and appropriate monitoring”. On substance, considerations of predictability and countercyclicality would appear to advise the use of changes (as opposed to levels) and planned inflation and GDP (see N Benalal, M Freier, W Melin, S Van Parys, L Reiss, ‘Towards a Single Fiscal Performance Indicator in the EU’s Fiscal Governance Framework’ (*European Central Bank Occasional Paper* 228, January 2022)).

The general escape clause allows the Council, on recommendation from the Commission, to adopt, within four weeks as a rule, a recommendation “Member States to deviate from their net expenditure path, in the event of a severe economic downturn in the euro area or the Union as a whole, provided it does not endanger fiscal sustainability in the medium term.” The allowed deviation is subject to “a one-year time limit”, which can be extended, on recommendation by the Commission, “provided that the severe economic downturn in the euro area or the Union as a whole persists.” While repeated extensions are possible, “each extension shall be for an additional period of one year at most.” As long as the situation giving rise to the activation of the escape clause persists, the Commission should “continue to monitor debt sustainability and ensure policy coordination and a consistent policy mix that takes into account the euro area and the Union dimension.”⁸¹

The national escape clause allows, with the same modalities as for the general escape clause, “a Member State to deviate from its net expenditure path where exceptional circumstances outside the control of the Member State lead to a major impact on the public finances of the Member State concerned, provided it does not endanger fiscal sustainability in the medium term.” The allowed deviation is subject to a “specif[ie]d time limit”, which can be extended “provided that the exceptional circumstances persist”, with each extension however being granted “for an additional period of one year at most.”⁸²

The escape clauses represent a rationalization of existing provisions in the preventive arm allowing for a temporary departure from the adjustment path towards the MTO when considering the annual updates of the medium-term plans (stability and convergence programmes) or when assessing compliance with the planned adjustment. The main difference with respect to the existing provisions concerns the explicit ex ante authorization of the Council that is required to activate the clause and to extend it beyond its otherwise strict time limit. This specification may reflect dissatisfaction with the modalities of activation and prolongation of the general escape clause during and after the COVID-19 crisis, which were not the subject of a specific Council decisions. At the same time, the soft coordination of fiscal policies by the Commission envisaged as long as the escape clause is activated reflects the practice followed during the COVID-19 crisis.

6. The new corrective arm of the Stability and Growth Pact

As its title suggests, the Proposal for amending Regulation 1467/97 contains much less innovations than the Proposal for Repealing Regulation 1466/97. Changes in the corrective arm are essentially meant to reflect the implications of the overhaul of the preventive arm, in particular, for Member States with debt in excess of 60% of GDP, which are potentially subject to EDP for breach of the debt criterion. More in general, the new corrective arm seeks to achieve a better coordination with the new preventive arm, including in terms of definitions.

The most important changes concern the regulation of the conditions for the opening of the EDP, in particular, for breach of the debt criterion (debt-based EDP).

⁸¹ Article 24 of Proposal for repealing Regulation 1466/97 < <https://www.ecb.europa.eu/pub/pdf/scpops/ecb.op288~b3b265ed14.en.pdf> > accessed 3 January 2024.

⁸² Art. 25 of Proposal for repealing and replacing Regulation 1466/97.

The condition for satisfying the debt criterion of the EDP, which the current regulation formulates in terms the ‘5% debt reduction benchmark’, is reduced to the condition that “the Member State concerned respects its net expenditure path”. In turn, it is specified that, for the Commission to prepare a report in accordance with Article 126(3) TFEU, which is the preliminary step before the possible opening of the EDP, the debt ratio should exceed the (60% of GDP) reference value, the budgetary position should not be close to balance or in surplus and “deviation recorded in the control account should either exceed (a) 0,3 percentage points of GDP annually, or (b) 0,6 percentage points of GDP cumulatively.”⁸³

The specification of the debt ratio threshold appears superfluous, as the Treaty makes clear that only Member States with debt ratio in excess of the reference value can be in breach of the debt criterion.

The specification of the threshold for the deviation from the net expenditure path to trigger the preliminary step of the EDP appears to reflect the intention of limiting the discretion of the Commission at the very early stage of the procedure.

The specification excluding the possible opening of a debt-based procedure if the budgetary position is close to balance or in surplus is potentially more problematic.

The notion of close to balance or in surplus corresponds to the MTO of the preventive arm of the SGP before the reform, which the proposed reform eliminates in favour of country-specific debt trajectories and net expenditure paths⁸⁴. A more substantial question emerges when one considers that a Member State might be able to depart significantly from its net expenditure path while obtaining a budgetary position of close to balance or in surplus. This might not be unlikely if the economy was experiencing a strong expansion led by domestic demand, particularly if driven by assets appreciation, in turn resulting in large revenue windfalls flattering budgetary outcomes, bearing also in mind that the budgetary position is measured in nominal terms, that is, not adjusted for the state of the cycle. This possibility – and its reverse, namely, revenue shortfalls – is precisely the reason why the net expenditure indicator takes into account only discretionary measures on the revenue side excluding changes in revenues outside the control of the government.

De-activating the net expenditure indicator as possible trigger of the EDP if revenue windfalls are sufficiently large to balance the budget runs counter the avowed aim of the reform of making fiscal policy less pro-cyclical, moreover in an asymmetric fashion, i.e., by disincentivizing the building of buffers in good times.

The formulation of the condition for satisfying the debt criterion of the EDP solely in terms of respect of the net expenditure path deserves some consideration.

It may appear contentious, at least first sight, that the debt criterion, which the Treaty defines in terms of debt ratio “sufficiently diminishing and approaching the reference value at a satisfactory pace”, should be effectively re-defined without any reference to the trajectory of debt. In other words, a Member State may be respecting its net expenditure path while its debt is increasing, and vice versa.

⁸³ Article 2(1a) as amended by Proposal amending Regulation 1467/97.

⁸⁴ To obviate this lacuna, Recital 15 of Proposal amending Regulation 1467 specifies that “the budgetary position shall be considered close to balance if the headline deficit does not exceed 0,5 percentage points of GDP.”⁸⁴

The apparent contradiction can be overcome by noting that respect of the net expenditure path should result in debt being put on a plausibly downward path in the medium term, as the net expenditure path is precisely calibrated to achieve that objective.

The reformulation of the debt criterion in terms of net expenditure path therefore can be considered to be admissible, or even constitute an improvement, in the sense that it aims at the correction of the underlying trend in debt, ignoring short-term and cyclical influences (an aim that is however partially contradicted by excluding the triggering of a debt-based EDP in case of a budgetary position of close to a balance or in surplus).

A more subtle question is whether a deviation from the net expenditure path can be the trigger of a debt-based EDP, to the extent that the net expenditure path is constrained by requirements that are not pertaining to the debt criterion itself. This is the case of the deficit resilience safeguard, which introduces a requirement that is additional to those related to the level and trajectory of debt (i.e., the common risk-based requirements and the further debt sustainability safeguard) and is explicitly and solely motivated on grounds of providing a “common resilience margin ... relative to 3% of GDP Treaty reference value” (see Section 4.2.1).

The act of opening an EDP for breach of the debt criterion when the breach occurs only in relation to a requirement explicitly related to the deficit criterion (the deficit resilience safeguard) would arguably represent a case of misuse of powers, as the act would be adopted with the purpose of achieving an end (protecting against the breach of the deficit criterion) other than stated in the procedure (protecting against a breach of the debt criterion). If retained, this argument would make illegal to enforce the deficit resilience safeguard through the EDP. The mere existence of the legal risk may induce a cautious approach by Commission when taking into account the “relevant factors” before deciding to propose, or not to, the opening of an EDP for breach of the debt criterion.

The provisions regarding the assessment of the relevant factors by the Commission and the Council when deciding on the opening of an EDP and, in the positive, on the ensuing EDP recommendation, are broadly in line with those in the current EDP regulation.

In particular, the opening of the EDP for breach of the deficit criterion retains a high degree of automaticity for Member States whose debt exceeds 60% of GDP. For these, taking into account all the “relevant factors” before deciding to open the EDP (or rather not to) continues to be ruled out, unless the breach of the deficit threshold is temporary and the level of the deficit remains close to the threshold.⁸⁵

The main innovations concern the introduction of, as aggravating factors, the “degree of public debt challenges” and “the size of the deviation from the net expenditure path”, with “substantial debt challenges” being considered as a key aggravating factor. However, the regulation introduces as mitigating factors, “the progress in the implementation of reforms and investments ... including those, supported by [NGEU], and the overall quality of public finances, in particular the effectiveness of national budgetary frameworks” and “the increase

⁸⁵ Article 2(4) as amended by Proposal amending Regulation 1467/97.

of government investment in defence, where applicable, considering also the time of recording of military equipment expenditure.”⁸⁶

The conditions for opening an EDP clarify that the excess over the 3% of GDP deficit threshold should be considered as “exceptional” if resulting from the circumstances giving rise to the activation by the Council of the general escape clause or the national escape clause. In turn, as these circumstances allow Member States to deviate from their net expenditure paths, “the Commission and the Council may decide ... not to conclude on the existence of an excessive deficit.”⁸⁷ These provisions appear to codify the practice followed during the COVID-19 crisis, when no EDP was opened in spite of large and persistent breaches of the deficit criterion, consistent with the formulation of the escape clauses in the new preventive arm.

The provisions governing the steps of the EDP following its opening are broadly in line with those in the current EDP regulation. In particular, the same tight timelines and specifications continue to apply to both the decisions to be adopted by the institutions and the actions to be taken in response by the concerned Member State at the different stages of the procedure.

The main differences reflect the introduction of the net expenditure path as the metrics for assessing the action taken by the concerned Member State in response to the EDP recommendation, including its implications for the debt-based EDP, at every stage of the procedure. Specifically:

- Both the (initial) EDP recommendation in accordance to Art. 126(7) and, in case of no effective action (for euro area Member States), the ‘stepping up’ of the procedure with a notice in accordance with Article 126(9) are to establish a deadline for the correction of the excessive deficit⁸⁸ and prescribe a net expenditure path to that effect.
- The correction of the excessive deficit should ensure the “the general government deficit remains or is brought or maintained below the [3% of GDP] reference value.” If the EDP was opened based on the deficit criterion (deficit-based EDP), it is further prescribed that the net expenditure path should “be consistent with a minimum annual structural adjustment of at least 0,5% of GDP as a benchmark”, with transitional

⁸⁶ Article 2(3) as amended by Proposal amending Regulation 1467/97. Regarding the degree of public debt challenges, it is further specified that it should be assessed based on the same methodology as for assessing the plausibility of the debt projections associated with the technical trajectories or the equivalent technical information (produced by the Commission in its early guidance under the preventive arm). The specification on the methodology for assessing debt challenges seems to conflate the methodology for projecting debt with that for assessing sustainability risk. The available methodology for assessing sustainability risk is found in the Commission Sustainability Monitor. It incorporates a methodology for projecting debt, which, according to Article 8 of the Proposal for Repealing Regulation 1466/97, is to serve as the methodology used for the production of the technical trajectories and the equivalent technical information, until the Council does not adopt the (final) methodology. The categorization of risk (where the existence substantial challenges seems to correspond to the high and intermediate medium-term risk categories of the Debt Sustainability Monitor of the Commission), however, demands additional assumptions and criteria.

⁸⁷ Article 2(5) as amended by Proposal amending Regulation 1467/97.

⁸⁸ Reflecting the experience of prevalingly multi-annual EDP, the revised provisions no longer contain the prescription that the correction of the excessive deficit should be completed in the year following its identification unless there are special circumstances.

provisions envisaged for the EDP opened in the first years from⁸⁹ or already opened at⁹⁰ the time into entry to force of the reform. For debt-based EDPs, the objective of the correction of the excessive deficit is not explicitly defined, but it is prescribed that “the corrective net expenditure path shall be at least as demanding as the net expenditure path adopted by the Council in [the fiscal structural plan according to new the preventive arm], and correct as a rule the cumulated deviations of the control account by the deadline set by the Council.”⁹¹

- The EDP should come to an end, that is, the Council should take a decision to “abrogate” the procedure, where: i) in case of deficit-based EDP, “the deficit has been brought below the [3% of GDP] reference value and is projected by the Commission to remain so in the current and following year”; ii) in case of debt-based EDP, “the Member State concerned respected the corrective net expenditure path set by the Council [in the recommendation under Article 126(7) TFEU or the notice under Article 126(9) TFEU]⁹².

Taken together, the provisions suggest some tentative conclusions: First, for deficit-based EDPs, the difference with the existing procedure reduces essentially in the reformulation of the action prescribed in the terms of (change in) net expenditure. The additional requirement that the net expenditure path should be consistent with a 0.5% of GDP change in the structural balance is a source of more apparent than real complication: on ex ante basis, that is, at the moment of the formulation of the EDP recommendation, and for the macro-fiscal scenario underlying it, there will be a correspondence between targets for the nominal deficit,

⁸⁹ Recital 24bis states that “the Commission may, for a transitory period in 2025, 2026 and 2027 – in order not to compromise the positive effects of the Recovery and Resilience Facility – adjust the [0.5% of GDP adjustment] benchmark to take into account the increase in interest payments when setting the proposed corrective path relating to the first medium-term fiscal-structural plan for the years 2025, 2026 and 2027 within the Excessive Deficit Procedure, provided the Member State concerned fulfils the conditions [on the delivery of the main challenges identified in the European Semester, and in particular, the country-specific recommendations and the common priorities of the Union].” Note however that, according to established practice, the qualifier “as a benchmark” is meant to allow the Commission to depart from the 0.5% adjustment benchmark provided that adequate justification is given.

⁹⁰ For Member States that find themselves subject to EDP at the time of entry into force of the reform (Article 17b as amended by Proposal amending Regulation 1467/97). Specifically, such Member States would receive “a revised [EDP] recommendation under Article 126(7) or a revised notice under Article 126(9)”, depending on the stage of the procedure they find themselves and that the revised EDP recommendations should be adopted “together with the adoption of the recommendation [endorsing the fiscal structural plan].” Recital 24 explains that existing EDP recommendations “need to be revised in order to align them with the [amended] provisions [on the EDP recommendations].” Assuming, in line with the announced exclusion of the opening of debt-based EDP upon the de-activation of the general escape clause in 2024, that only (deficit-based) EDPs are concerned, considerations legal certainty and legitimate expectations, which are general principles of EU law, would appear to rule out that the revised EDP recommendations could prescribe an adjustment path more demanding than the one already prescribed to bring the deficit below the 3% of GDP threshold. The additional transitional provisions allowing for a temporary easing of the minimum benchmark adjustment of 0.5% of GDP are another reason to exclude that the revised EDP recommendation could prescribe a faster pace of adjustment such as could be required to satisfy the requirements of new preventive arm within the normal (or possibly even the extended) horizon of the first cohort fiscal-structural plans. Therefore, the transitional provisions seem to confirm that the opening of the EDPs would make the initial fiscal-structural plans, in particular, for high-debt Member States more lenient than one should otherwise expect.

⁹¹ Article 3(4) as amended by Proposal amending Regulation 1467/97.

⁹² Article 8(3) as amended by Proposal amending Regulation 1467/97.

the structural deficit, and the change in net expenditure necessary to achieve the targets.⁹³ On an ex post basis, that is, at the moment of assessing compliance with the recommendation in terms of effective action, only the delivery of the prescribed change in net expenditure will be taken into account. This conclusion is strongly suggested by the parallelism between the preventive and the corrective arm, which the proposed reform aims to increase.

Secondly, for debt-based EDPs, the procedure could be described as enforcing the fiscal-structural plan by other means, as the change in the net expenditure path should have the objective of correcting the deviations accumulated from the plan, which have led to the opening of the EDP. Taken to its logical conclusion, this objective should imply that the deadline for correction of the excessive deficit should be no earlier than the year of the expected fulfilment of the requirements for the fiscal-structural plan, i.e., the common risk-based requirements and the additional debt sustainability and deficit-resilience safeguards (with the above-mentioned caveat on the legal enforceability of the deficit-resilience safeguard). This might translate in very long EDPs, however.

Thirdly, the provision for the abrogation of deficit-based EDPs confirms the intrinsic ‘nominal bias’ of the procedure: a government that has durably reached the nominal target of 3% of GDP is entitled to the abrogation of the EDP, irrespective for whether or not it has delivered the prescribed action in terms of change in the net expenditure path. In turn, applying recursively the same logic, it should be excluded that the EDP could be stepped up as long as the annual deficit targets are met.⁹⁴

Finally, the provision for the abrogation for debt-based EDPs make sufficiently clear that the concerned Member State cannot not leave the EDP if does not respect the net expenditure path. However, as noted, it is not clear for how long the net expenditure path should be respected before the EDP could be abrogated. Nor is it clear whether a deviation from the net expenditure path in the recommendation should necessarily lead to the stepping up of the EDP, or, on grounds of parallelism with the deficit-based EDP, meeting intermediate nominal targets could avoid it.⁹⁵

Revised provisions are also included allowing the Council, on a recommendation by the Commission, to revise the EDP recommendation or notice addressed to a Member State, “in particular to extend the deadline for correction by one year as a rule”, irrespective of the

⁹³ The correspondence established by the amended Article 3(4) between net expenditure path and change in the structural balance is a further reason for interpreting the net expenditure path in terms of change rather than levels (see also Section 4.2.4 above).

⁹⁴ The Code of Conduct of the Stability and Growth Pact states (p.15) “For legal reasons, a deficit-based EDP cannot be stepped up if the Member State achieves its intermediate headline deficit target, even when the recommended change in the structural balance is not achieved. At the same time, though, a careful analysis should still be conducted to better understand the nature of the underlying budgetary developments.” The same reasoning would seem to apply in the new corrective arm, although the amended provisions do not mention any more intermediate budgetary targets in the EDP n. These should however be naturally derived from the information contained in the recommendations.

⁹⁵ The noted ‘nominal bias’ of the deficit-based EDP and the single character of the procedure (i.e., although the condition for opening and closing the EDP differ in relation to deficit and debt criterion, the procedure is meant to be the same) suggest that intermediate deficit targets should be included in the recommendation, in line with the current set-up. Concerning the condition for the abrogation of a debt-based EDP, the Commission Proposal for a Council regulation amending Regulation (EC) No 1467/97 envisaged that a debt-based EDP should be abrogated if “the Member State concerned respected the corrective net expenditure path set by the Council [in the recommendation under Article 126(7) TFEU or the notice under Article(9) TFEU] over the previous 2 years and is projected to continue to do so in the current year on the basis of the Commission forecast.” The time limit reflected the concern of avoiding excessively long EDPs.

delivery of effective action, if the conditions for the activation by the Council of the general escape clause or the national escape clause apply.⁹⁶ The provisions update provisions existing since the Six-Pack reform, which are meant to avoid establishing no effective action, with the consequences in terms of stepping up of the procedure and imposition of sanctions (for euro area Member States) and macroeconomic conditionality, when exceptional economic and fiscal circumstances argue for a different orientation of fiscal policy.

Finally, the new corrective arm contains revised provisions concerning the sanctions: in accordance with Article 126(11) TFEU, the Council, on recommendation by the Commission can impose on a euro area Member State sanctions in case of repeated failure to take effective action, namely, in response to a notice addressed to it by the Council in accordance to Article 126(9) TFEU. The amount of the sanctions that the Council should impose is limited to “up to 0.05% of the latest estimate of the previous year’s GDP for a 6-month period and be paid every 6 months until the Council assesses that the Member State concerned has taken effective action in response to the notice issued under Article 126(9) TFEU.”⁹⁷

As explained in the recitals “the fines provided for in Article 126(11) TFEU should not provide for a minimum amount but they should accumulate until effective action is taken.”⁹⁸ In turn, the Council should abrogate the sanctions “depending on the significance of the progress made by the participating Member State concerned in correcting the excessive deficit.”⁹⁹ This incrementalistic approach corresponds to the idea, already advanced in the initial orientations for reform by the Commission, that “the effective use of financial sanctions would be de-constrained by lowering their amounts.”¹⁰⁰

There is reason to be concerned, however, that a stumbling block to the enforcement of the EDP may materialise at an earlier stage of the procedure, namely, with the decision under Art. 126(8) TFEU establishing a Member State’s failure to take effective action in response to the initial recommendation under the EDP. This decision has in fact become the potential trigger of multiple consequences – in terms of early fines based on euro-area secondary legislation,¹⁰¹ suspension of funds under the ESFF and the RRF¹⁰² and lastly, loss of

⁹⁶ Article 3(6)(b) and Article 5(2)(b) as amended by Proposal amending Regulation 1467/97.

⁹⁷ Article 12 as amended by Proposal for Regulation amending Regulation 1467/97. In the current set-up a Member State failing to take action in response to a notice under Article 126(9) TFEU faces in principle an annual fine equal to 0.2% of its GDP in the preceding year plus a variable component determined by the magnitude of its excessive deficit, up to a maximum of 0.5% of GDP. Note that Regulation No 1173/2011 of the European Parliament and of the Council on the effective enforcement of budgetary surveillance in the euro area (effective enforcement of budgetary surveillance regulation) [2011] OJ L306, adopted as a part of the Six-Pack reform and applying only to euro area Member States, mandates the Commission to propose a fine of 0.2% of GDP in case of a Council decision establishing (in accordance with Article 126(8) TFEU) no effective action in response to the initial ED recommendation. The drastic reduction of the fines envisaged in the amended Regulation 1467/97 would seem to call for a parallel revision, if not an elimination, of the early sanctions introduced by the Six-Pack.)

⁹⁸ Recital 21 of Proposal amending Regulation 1467/97.

⁹⁹ Article 14 as amended by Proposal amending Regulation 1467/97.

¹⁰⁰ Communication on orientations for a reform of the EU economic governance framework COM/2022/583 final, p.17.

¹⁰¹ See note 112.

¹⁰² While formally not having the character of sanctions, the structural conditionalities envisaged by the legal framework regulating the European Structural and Investment Funds (ESIF) have a potential far-reaching impact on recipient Member States found not to comply with their obligation under the EDP. Specifically Regulation No 1303/2013 of the European Parliament and of the Council laying down common provisions ... and general provisions on [the Funds] (Common Provisions Regulation) [2013] L347/320 and amendments

eligibility for government security purchases by the ECB under the Transmission Protection Mechanism (TPI)¹⁰³ – whose macroeconomic significance may greatly exceed that of the sanctions envisaged by the Treaty.

Enforcement is therefore likely to remain the most intractable issue with EU fiscal rules.

7. Conclusions

The Treaty does not give to the EU the power to directly interfere with national budgets and EU fiscal rules cannot be enforced via the Court of Justice. This makes EU fiscal governance more akin to a form of organized peer pressure than genuine supranational decision-making.

Within the limits set by the Treaty and the underlying political realities, the orientations for the reform put forward by the Commission in 2023, coming after the breakthrough of NGEU, represent the most radical overhaul of fiscal governance since the creation of the Stability and Growth Pact. They make debt sustainability the direct objective of the fiscal rules, dispensing with artificial numerical benchmarks (apart the historic 3% of GDP deficit threshold) and Member States' medium-term fiscal structural plans, combining fiscal adjustments with structural reform and investment commitments, the centrepiece of surveillance.

The draft legislation agreed by the Council traduces in part the original spirit of the reform, by introducing numerical safeguards over and above the constraints justified by debt sustainability, which risk compromising the national ownership of the plans, specifically, by high-debt Member States. However, the reform greatly simplifies surveillance, at least in two respects: for low-debt Member States, the prescriptions of the preventive arm of the SGP effectively cease to exist and what is left is only the EDP for breach of the 3% of GDP deficit threshold; for all Member States, once the plans are in place, there is only a single observable indicator that matters for compliance, the net expenditure path.

While the promotion of reforms and investments is a much-touted goal of the reform, and the one where the interplay with NGEU is most evident, the reform confirms the primacy of fiscal sustainability: the trade-off between fiscal adjustment and reforms and investment is only about a limited extension of the timescale of the adjustment, not in its eventual size in the medium term. The reform therefore is vulnerable to the criticism that the focus on debt reduction come at the expense of the green transition, especially after the exceptional funding made available by the RRF comes to an end.

Article 23(9)-(12) envisages the suspension of commitments or payments under the ESIF in case of a Council decision establishing (in accordance with Article 126(8) TFEU) no effective action to correct the excessive deficit, with further suspension envisaged for euro-area Member State found (in accordance with Article 126(11) TFEU) not to comply with a notice to take measures. Similar provisions are included in the RRF regulation (Article 10). In both cases, the decision to suspend (and to revoke the suspension) is adopted by the Council on proposal by the Commission, according to reverse qualified majority. The provisions have not been put in practice to date.

¹⁰³ According to the statement the Governing Council of the ECB establishing the TPI the first of the eligibility criteria is “compliance with the EU fiscal framework: not being subject to an excessive deficit procedure (EDP), or not being assessed as having failed to take effective action in response to an EU Council recommendation under Article 126(7) of the Treaty on the Functioning of the European Union (TFEU)” (‘The Transmission Protection Instrument’ (ECB, 21 July 2021) < <https://www.ecb.europa.eu/press/pr/date/2022/html/ecb.pr220721~973e6e7273.en.html> > accessed 7 January 2024.

Implementation and enforcement have historically been the weakest link of the system of fiscal governance. There is a risk that the additional constraints in the design of the rules may be offset by a reduced commitment in their implementation by Member States and their enforcement by the Commission and the Council. The perhaps inevitably ambiguous provisions on revising the fiscal plans are likely to provide an early test. While the lowering of the sanctions in the EDP is meant to facilitate their eventual imposition, the concentration of potential negative consequences for a Member State found in non-compliance at an earlier stage of the procedure continue to raise doubts on the willingness of the Commission and the Council to escalate the procedure.